

Spectrophotometric Determination of Mo(VI) with Benzohydroxamic acid

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A rapid method for the simultaneous solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of micro amounts of hexavalent molybdenum with benzohydroxamic acid is described. The intense yellow-greenish coloured complex thus extracted from hexanol at pH 2.0 absorbs at around 370 nm. A clear cut separation from many commonly occurring metal ions is easily accomplished. Effect of acidity, reagent concentration and diverse ions on the visible absorption of the extracted complex have also been investigated.

BENZOHYDROXAMIC acid (BHA) has been found to be an excellent reagent for the solvent extraction and colorimetric determination of many metal ions¹⁻⁵. Recently Agrawal *et al* reported the solvent extraction and photometric determination of Ti(IV) with BHA⁶. No attempt seems to have been made for the extraction photometric determination of Mo(VI) with BHA, especially on micro concentration level. In this paper we report a rapid method for the simultaneous solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of micro amounts of molybdenum with BHA. The intense yellow-greenish coloured complex thus extracted from hexanol absorbs at around 370 nm where the reagent as well as the molybdenum ion have no absorption. The advantage of the proposed method lies in the fact that a clean cut separation from many commonly occurring metal ions is easily accomplished, and it is equally applicable for the extraction of tracer amounts of molybdenum. Examination on the effect of acidity, reagent concentration and diverse ions on the absorption of molybdenum-BHA complex were carried out.

Experimental

Apparatus: The spectra of the molybdenum(VI) complexes were scanned on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer and measurements at constant wavelengths were performed on a Beckman DU quartz spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched silica cells. pH adjustments were done with a Radiometer pH meter.

Reagents and solutions: BHA was synthesized by the method of Blatt⁷. It was recrystallized before use from ethyl acetate and was dried in vacuum over P₂O₅. Its final purity was checked by melting point, element analysis, UV and IR spectra. Generally, a 0.1 M reagent solution in water used for all extraction work. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from reagent grade salts using the procedure of West⁸.

Extraction procedures: In a separating funnel, 2 ml of molybdenum solution was placed and 8 ml of

Conc. HCl added (10 N). Then 10 ml of reagent solution was added and a yellow-greenish coloured complex was formed. Then 10 ml of 1-hexanol was added and the contents were shaken for 5 min. The phases were allowed to settle and separate, and the organic phase was carefully transferred to a 25 ml flask after drying it over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Extraction was repeated twice to ensure complete recovery of molybdenum. Finally the extracts were diluted to 25 ml with hexanol. The absorbance of the yellow-greenish coloured complex was measured at 370 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of molybdenum was then computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum: The visible absorption spectrum of a solution of molybdenum(VI)-BHA complex (Mo = 21.8 µg/ml) extracted at pH 2.0 showed strong absorbance at 370 nm (Fig. 1). The reagent blank showed no absorbance at this wave length. All absorbance measurements were therefore taken at 370 nm. Optical density-concentration graphs were plotted by from these measurements; they showed that the coloured hexanol extracts obey Beer's Law within the usual 1-5% error of photometric measurements.

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra of Benzohydroxamic Acid Complex

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Extraction as a function of pH : The liquid-liquid extraction behaviour of molybdenum(VI) BHA system was studied in the pH range from 1-6 (Table 1, Fig. 2). The results given in Table show that the extraction commenced at pH 1.0 and it was quantitative at around pH 2-3. The coloured chelate was formed instantaneously and was stable at least for four weeks.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the Extraction

TABLE-1 EXTRACTION OF MOLYBDENUM(VI) - BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEX AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Extraction E (%)	Distribution ratio D
1.0	100	—
1.5	100	—
2.0	100	—
2.2	100	—
2.5	95	19.00
3.0	80	17.00
4.0	50	11.00
4.5	30	6.00
5.0	15	2.5

Conformity with Beer's law : Molybdenum and benzohydroxamic acid solution were prepared at various concentrations and extracted from 1-hexanol. This system obeys Beer's law over the range of 0.5 to 40 µg/ml of molybdenum when extracted from 1-hexanol. The molar absorptivity at 370 nm is 2.2×10^3 .

Effect of reagent concentration : Hexavalent molybdenum was extracted at pH 2.0 with varying volume and concentration of the reagent. The results indicate that a single extraction with 10 ml of 0.1 M BHA was quite adequate for quantitative extraction, while extraction was incomplete with 0.005, 0.01 and 0.015 M reagent solutions. Larger excesses of reagent could be used without any difficulty. In practice, 10 ml of 0.1 M BHA was always used for extraction purposes.

Effect of diverse ions : In order to examine the utility of this method in the presence of other ions, their interference was studied. At first the effect of various ions on the Mo(VI)-BHA absorption maximum

at 370 nm was investigated. Table-2 summarised the absorbance and the position of the absorption maximum. Moderate amounts of many commonly associated ions with molybdenum were tolerable. The ions showing strong interference include V^{+5} , Co^{+4} , Ti^{+4} and Fe^{+3} .

Extraction time and stability of colour : Variation from 1 to 5 min. in the shaking period revealed that 95% extraction of the coloured complex from the aqueous phase occurred in 1 min. whereas beyond 2 min. quantitative extraction could be accomplished as per extraction procedure. The hexanol extracts of the complex were quite stable over a period of 4-5 weeks.

Stoichiometry of the Mo(VI) BHA Complex : It is evident that the extraction of Mo(VI) solution of bidentate chelating agent in organic solvents involves the formation of electrically neutral complex with general formula $MoO_2A_2^{0-1.1}$. The corresponding reaction with benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) is

$$k_2 = \frac{[MoO_2A_2] aq}{[MoO_2^{2+} aq.][A^-]_2 aq.} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } \lambda MA = \frac{[MoO_2A_2] org.}{[MoO_2A_2] aq} \quad \dots(2)$$

where : aq = aqueous ; org = organic phase ; A^- = anion of BHA ; k_2 = instability constant and MA = distribution constant of complex.

The ratio of Mo(VI) to BHA was studied by Job's continuous variation method and molar ratio method indicate that the complex consists of 2 molecules of BHA for each atom of molybdenum and the structure of the complex can be represented as

Further the stability constants was calculated from eq. (1) and (2) have the value of $\log \beta_2 = 25.98$.

Nature of the Extracted Species : For studying the composition of the extracted species the solid complex was isolated by slowly evaporating off the organic phase (Hexanol). It was analysed by microanalysers for C, H, and N. The results obtained corresponded to the formula $MoO_2(C_7H_9NO_2)_2$ and gave a metal to ligand ratio $MoO_2 : BHA : 1:2$.

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